

Utilizing Complexity Metrics During Code Reviews to Promote Software Sustainability

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EXASCALE COMPUTING PROJECT

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Software Sustainability

- Definitions

- Cost Efficient Maintainability and Evolvability

-- Sehestedt, et al.

- Capacity of the software to endure

-- Software Sustainability Institute proposal

- Types

- Intrinsic: Pertaining to characteristics of the software

- Extrinsic: Pertaining to the software development environment

-- Rosado de Souza, et al.

Sustainability Factors

How ...

extensible
interoperable
maintainable
portable
reusable
scalable
usable

Introduction

- Software sustainability is key to Computational Science and Engineering (CSE)
 - Projects often begin as a research activity, but sometimes have a long useful life
 - Cutting-edge algorithms and language features -> inherent complexity
 - Performance on new supercomputers
 - Large code bases
- There are many challenges to CSE software sustainability
 - Complex designs
 - Funding models
 - Developer training
- **Question:** Can complexity metrics aid in the quality and efficiency of code reviews? (Note complexity should not be used as the sole basis for decisions.)
- We postulated that areas of high, and particularly increasing, complexity merit special consideration during code reviews

Motivation

- Technical debt builds up over time
- Previous work[1] measured complexity, and identified areas of high complexity, but didn't seem actionable in a practical way
- A complex code base is detrimental to software maintainability [2] and sustainability
- Inadequate code reviews decrease software quality [3] and increase maintenance burden [4]

[1] Willenbring, J., Walia, G. Evaluating the Sustainability of Computational Science and Engineering Software: Empirical Observations. In *34th International Conference on Software Engineering & Knowledge Engineering, SEKE 2022 – Proceedings* (pp 453-456). KSI Research.

[2] Boehm, B. *Software Engineering Economics*, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, 1981.

[3] McIntosh, S., Kamei, Y., Adams, B., & Hassan, A. E. (2014). The impact of code review coverage and code review participation on Software quality: A case study of the Qt, VTK, and ITK projects. In *11th Working Conference on Mining Software Repositories, MSR 2014 - Proceedings* (pp. 192-201). Association for Computing Machinery, Inc.

[4] Eisty, N.U., Carver, J.C. Developers perception of peer code review in research software development. *Empir Software Eng* 27, 13 (2022).

Experiment Design

- We analyzed seven pull requests (PRs) from each of two open source scientific software projects using Metrix++
 - Open repository
 - Substantial history
 - Important in CSE community
 - Members of the Extreme-Scale Scientific Software Development Kit (xSDK)
 - Receive funding through the DOE's Exascale Computing Project (ECP)
 - ECP has a strong interest in software sustainability
 - Different primary development institutions
 - Documentation or infrastructure focused pull requests were not considered
 - Pull requests were of different sizes, from small to large
 - Projects were anonymized
 - GitHub Action used to automate collection of metrics using Metrix++

Project Descriptions

- Project 1
 - Linear and non-linear solvers and preconditioners for PDEs
 - Primarily written in C
 - More than 800,000 lines of code
- Project 2
 - A collection of solvers and enabling technologies used for large-scale, complex multi-physics engineering and scientific problems
 - Primarily written in C++
 - More than 4,000,000 lines of code

Approach

- Considered complexity of code regions (classes, functions, structs, namespaces, etc)
- Complexity thresholds:
 - 10 – complexity is not a significant concern
 - 20, 30, 40 – elevated complexity
 - 50 - untestable
 - 75 – significant risk of a “bad fix”
- Thresholds may be customized to individual project or organization needs

Metrics

- Lines of code added and deleted by each PR
- Number of code regions above each threshold after the PR “touched” by the PR
- Number of code regions above each threshold after the PR with complexity increased due to the PR (using Metrix++ “trend” option)
- Example Metrix++ command:

```
metrix++ limit --db-file=proj1.after.complex.db  
--db-file-prev=proj1.before.complex.db  
--max-limit=std.code.complexity:cyclomatic:50  
--warn-mode=touched
```

Using the Results During Code Reviews

Threshold description →

Identify location in code →

How complex is the region? →

How much complexity was added? →

Added and existing complexity are related, but different concerns

No strict rules for using these metrics!
Useful for guiding reviewer's attention

```
Run Metrix++
succeeded on Mar 7 in 1m 33s

10 plus complexity regions trending up 0s

28 Metric name : std.code.complexity:cyclomatic
29 Region name : P...p_E...OS
30 Metric value : 35
31 Modified : True
32 Change trend : +20
33 Limit : 10.0
34 Suppressed : False
35
36 ./:: info: 3 regions exceeded the limit
   'std.code.complexity:cyclomatic' > 10.0 [applied to 'any'
   region type(s)]
37
38 Error: Process completed with exit code 3.
```

Fig. 1. Metrix++ GitHub Action Output

Results

TABLE I
HOTSPOT COMPLEXITY DATA

PR	Proj	Added	Removed	10 To	10 Tr	20 To	20 Tr	30 To	30 Tr	40 To	40 Tr	50 To	50 Tr	75 To	75 Tr
1	1	112	40	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
2	1	5279	448	20	15	11	8	7	4	4	2	4	2	1	0
3	1	332	299	7	0	3	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
4	1	383	37	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	1	387	94	5	3	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	0	0
6	1	15,220	14,875	1959	1	802	0	390	0	231	0	151	0	58	0
7	1	5336	424	6	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
8	2	8	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	2	1339	668	26	7	5	2	3	1	2	1	1	1	0	0
10	2	350	94	4	2	4	2	3	2	3	2	1	1	0	0
11	2	508	3	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	2	642	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	2	977	24	2	1	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	2	245	197	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Low Complexity PRs

PR	Proj	Added	Removed	10 To	10 Tr	20 To	20 Tr	30 To	30 Tr	40 To	40 Tr	50 To	50 Tr	75 To	75 Tr
8	2	8	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	2	642	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	2	245	197	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

- 0 regions of complexity greater than 10 (touched or trending)
 - Do not introduce or modify significant complexity
- 1 very small PR
- 2 medium sized PRs
 - 1 adds new code
 - 1 modifies existing
- PRs should still be reviewed for non-complexity reasons
 - Complexity is only one factor to consider during code reviews

Medium Complexity PRs

PR	Proj	Added	Removed	10 To	10 Tr	20 To	20 Tr	30 To	30 Tr	40 To	40 Tr	50 To	50 Tr	75 To	75 Tr
3	1	332	299	7	0	3	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
4	1	383	37	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	1	5336	424	6	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
11	2	508	3	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	2	977	24	2	1	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

- Elevated complexity that is still deemed testable
- Varying PR size
 - Medium to very large
- Some primarily new code, some primarily modified
- Don't ignore
 - Regions of code at lower thresholds
 - Code regions of low complexity

High Complexity PRs

PR	Proj	Added	Removed	10 To	10 Tr	20 To	20 Tr	30 To	30 Tr	40 To	40 Tr	50 To	50 Tr	75 To	75 Tr
1	1	112	40	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
2	1	5279	448	20	15	11	8	7	4	4	2	4	2	1	0
5	1	387	94	5	3	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	0	0
6	1	15,220	14,875	1959	1	802	0	390	0	231	0	151	0	58	0
9	2	1339	668	26	7	5	2	3	1	2	1	1	1	0	0
10	2	350	94	4	2	4	2	3	2	3	2	1	1	0	0

- These PRs have at least one region of untestable code
- Significant size variation
 - Largest PR is impractical to review thoroughly
- Some PRs have several regions to consider for complexity
- Consider breaking up large PRs with many complex regions
 - Might review commit by commit

Next Steps

- Conduct a case study on use of the approach
 - Ask participants to assess usefulness of metrics
 - for reviewing 3 PRs
 - more generally
- Study PRs focused primarily on code removal and cleanup
- Gather more data on tracking complexity over time
- Study metrics on a per-contributor level
 - Identify opportunities for coaching and training

PR #: *<link to PR>*

Changes to view: *<link to PR changes>*

Complex region # / #:

Name: *<name of code region>*

Location: *./<path to file>/<file_name>:<line #>*

Complexity: *<complexity of region>*

Increasing: *<Yes / No>*

Link: *<link to specific file in PR change list>*

Conclusion and Relevance to Industry

- Complexity metrics
 - measure complexity introduced by a PR
 - measure complexity present in regions of code impacted by a PR
 - indicate regions of most significant interest regarding complexity
 - can identify developers who would benefit from training in code design
 - can be used to monitor changes in complexity over time
 - support requests to break PRs into smaller pieces

Conclusion and Relevance to Industry

- Metrics can be used in support of broader sustainability analysis
 - Complexity **trends** over time represent **one aspect** of sustainability
 - Possible to measure complexity introduced by individual contributors
- Metrics can be used to guide PR review efforts
 - process and thresholds can be customized to organization/project needs
 - metric collection can be automated using a GitHub Action that calls Metrix++
- Data pertains to only complexity concerns – regions of code with low complexity cannot be ignored
 - Use metrics (generally, not just complexity) in an appropriate context
 - Many topics of concern for sustainability and code reviews are not addressed by this approach

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